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ATTITUDE OF TEACHERS TOWARDS IN –SERVICE TEACHER EDUCATION

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Abstract:

The present study was an attempt to find out the attitude of teacher educators towards in-service teacher education programmes. Investigator was focused to search the difference in attitude on the subject in question, between teacher educators serving in govt. / govt. aided Institutions and private/ self- financed organizations. A tool was developed by the investigator to measure the attitude of teachers towards in –service teacher education. 65- Teachers of B. Ed from both types of institutions were selected randomly for the study. The study reveals that both types of teachers had favorable and positive attitude towards in-service teacher education and gender did not play any role in respect of the variable in question.

.Key Words:

In-service Teacher Education, Govt., Aided Institution, Self-Finance Institution, Attitude, Orientation programme, Refresher course, Workshop Symposium, and Conference.

Since the dawn of independence, India has been attempting to raise the standard of living of its masses. The success of such efforts along with other factors depends to a great extent on the quality of manpower, which in turn is influenced by the standard of education in the country. The standard of education in the country depends above all other things, on the quality and competence of teachers. It is true to say that teacher is the heart of every educational institution and the success of an institution in the most significant feature in the learning environment provided by the institution. The present age is the age of technology which requires rapid changes and innovation (Fetcher-F et.al,1995), due to this demand of expert guidance of teachers has increased. To cope up this situation the in-service teacher training programmes are the necessary means to update the teacher's knowledge and competence to handle the day-to-day educational problems(Cox, M,et.al1988). These programmes can reconstruct the attitude of teachers resulting in the professional competence.

Canne (1969) has defined in-service teacher training programme as – “All those activities and course which aim at enhancing and strengthening the professional knowledge, interest and skill of in- service teachers.” Thus teacher education is continuous process and also equally important as the pre-service teachers training. Due to globalization and privatization; the quality aspect of teacher education is a matter of great concern. It has also given chances for the growth of teacher – education institutions in the private sector. Instead of all other things competitiveness has become a criterion for teacher education. Due to commercialization of education and marketing of services of teachers, teacher education and teaching require a radical transformation. Therefore in the present study an effort has been made to compare the attitudes of Govt. aided and self finance B.ED. College teachers towards in- service teacher training programmers.

Definition of The Terms Used : Teachers- The teachers serving in various BEd colleges/ departments of education in govt. or govt. aided college and self finance college are termed as teacher in the study

In – Service Teacher Education for B.Ed. College Teachers: Learning is a life- long process and cope up with the rapid changes being occurred in society, science and technologies, one should attend the in-service courses, which can help the teacher to modify his behavior. Realizing the fact various in-service programmes are governed by various agencies, a few of them are – 1. Orientation course . 2. Refresher course 3. Intensive course 4. Workshop 5. Symposium 6. Educational conferences etc.

Attitude : Attitude can be defined as positive or negative feeling, and relationship between an individual and psychological object.”

Objectives of the Study: The study has been designed to realize the following objectives:

1-To study the attitude of Govt. Aided B.Ed. College teachers towards in service teacher training programme. 02-To study the attitude of Self- finance B.Ed. College Teachers towards in service teacher training programme. 03-To compare the attitude of Govt. Aided & Self finance

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B.Ed. College Teachers towards in-service teacher training programme. 04- To compare the attitude of male and female B.Ed teachers towards in service teacher training programmes. 05-To compare the attitude of male teachers working in Govt. Aided & Self finance B.Ed. College towards in service teacher training programme. 06-To compare the attitude to female teachers working in Govt. Aided & Self finance B.Ed. Programmes towards in service teacher training programme.

Hypotheses of the Study: 01-The B.Ed. Teacher of Govt. Aided Colleges have favorable attitudes towards in service teacher training programmes. 02-The B.Ed. Teachers of Self finance Colleges have favorable attitudes towards in service teacher training programmes .03-There is no significant difference between attitude of Govt. Aided and Self finance B.Ed. College 04- Teachers towards In service teacher training programmes. 05-There is no significant difference between attitude of male & female B.Ed. College Teachers towards in service teacher training programmes. 06-There is no significant difference between attitude of Govt. Aided and Self Finance male B.Ed. College Teachers towards in service teacher training programmes .07-There is no significant difference between attitude of Govt. Aided and Self- finance B.Ed. College female Teachers towards in service teacher training progrmmes.

1-Delimitations of the Study: The Study was confounded to B.Ed. Colleges affiliated to Agra University,the samples size of 65 Teachers working in B.Ed. Colleges was taken .Only one variable i.e. attitude of teachers towards in-service teacher education was studied.

Sampling & Sample : A sample of 65 B.Ed. teachers was selected by stratified random sampling techniques, out of these 65 teachers, 31 teachers are from Govt. Aided Colleges and 34 are from Self finance institution. The total sample constitutes 27 male teachers (12 of Govt. aided & 15 of Self finance institutions) and 38 female teacher (19 of Govt. Aided & 19 of Self finance institutions.)

Tools Used: College Teachers Attitude towards the In-service teacher training education was developed by the investigation. Tools was named as “The Attitude of In-service Teacher training programme scale (AITTPS).The tool has 10 dimensions regarding attitude of teachers-

Curriculum of training, In-service teachers' motivation by colleagues, Monetary Assistance & administrative support, Use of In-service teacher education, Need of training, Utility of training, Time period of training, Outcome of training. Teachers' satisfaction from training.

Hypothesis-1 : *The B.Ed. Teachers of Govt. Aided College have favorable attitudes toward in-service teacher education programme.* **Table -01** : Attitude of Govt. B.Ed coll. teachers

SN.	Attitude Score	Frequency	Percentage
01	18	2	6.45
02	17	12	38.70
03	16	8	25.80
04	15	5	16.12
05	14	2	6.45
06	13	1	3.22
08	12	1	3.22
N=31	Mean=16	SD=1.37	

Analysis and Interpretation of Data: Table -1, contains data related to attitude of Teachers of Govt. aided College for assessing the attitude of teachers, Attitude Inventory for in-service Teachers Training programmes was administered to a total of 31 teachers of Govt. aided Colleges and they were scored as per the instructions given in the inventory. The score range in the inventory varied from a minimum of 0 (zero) to a maximum of 20 and obtained score of the attitude ranged from 12 to 18. From the above table it is evident that the mean value of attitude of teachers of Govt. aided colleges is 16 and SD is 1.37. The obtained mean value was higher than the theoretical mean value (10) of attitude inventory for In-service teacher training

programme (I.S.T.T.P.) furthermore 70.95% cases lie (greater than or equal to) $>$ mean. Which indicates that sample holds fairly good favorable attitude towards I.S.T.T.P. As the mean value in remarkable higher and S.D. is not too high. These two trends conjugation indicates that the hypotheses. “The B.Ed. teachers of Govt. Aided colleges have favorable attitude towards in-service teacher training programme.” is retained.

Hypothesis – 2 : *The B.Ed. teachers of Self finance colleges have favorable attitude towards In-service teacher education programme (ISTTP).*

Table-2 Attitude of self Finance. B.Ed coll. Teachers

SN.	Attitude Score	Frequency	Percentage
1	18	10	11.70
2	17	10	29.41
3	16	6	17.64
4	15	5	14.40
5	14	6	17.64
6	13	3	8.82
7	12	0	0
N=34	Mean=15.76	Sd=1.53	

Interpretation: Table 2 contains data relating attitude of Teachers of Self finance Colleges. For assessing the attitude of teachers, Attitude Inventory for In-service teacher training programme was administered to a total of 34 teachers of self finance colleges and they were scored as per the instructions mentioned in the inventory. The score range in the inventory varied from a minimum of 0 (zero) to a maximum of 20 and obtained mean value of attitude of teacher

of self finance colleges is 15.76 and SD is 1.53. The obtained mean value was higher than the theoretical mean value (10) of attitude inventory for I.S.T.T.P. furthermore 58.81% case lies (greater than or equal to) $>$ mean. Which indicates that sample holds fairly good favorable attitude toward I.S.T.T.P. as the mean value is remarkably high and SD is not to high. These two trends conjugation indicate that the hypotheses. “The B.Ed. Teachers of Self finance colleges have favorable attitudes towards in-service teacher training programmes.” is retained.

It is interesting to know that both Govt. Aided & Self finance B.Ed. teachers Possess favorable attitude towards in-service teacher training program: It means that actual performance & expectances of the individual teachers is about the same and it may be said that the person is realistic & practical in life.

Hypothesis – 3 *There is no significant difference between attitude of Govt. aided and Self finance B.Ed. college teachers towards in-service teacher education programmes.*

Table – 3 Comparison of attitude between Govt.& Self finance. Coll. teachers

Govt. Aided College Teachers (N ₁ =31)		Self finance College Teacher s (N ₂ =34)		Cr-Value
Mean(M ₁)	S.D.	Mean (M ₂)	S.D.	
16	1.37	15.76	153	CR = 0.672

Interpretation: Table No. 3 indicates that our calculated critical ratio value (CR) was 0.672 which is less than the critical value of both levels of significance (0.01 and 0.05 level) with 63 degree of freedom. So null the hypothesis has been accepted. Thus we can say that there is no significant difference between attitude of Govt. aided and self finance college teachers towards In-service teacher education programmes. Type of the institution [Govt. aided and Self finance] does not exert significant influence on the attitude of B.Ed. teachers towards In-service teacher training programmes. It means that the teachers of Govt. Aided and Self finance B.Ed. Colleges have the same attitude towards I.S.T.T.P.

Hypothesis- 4 : *There is no significant difference between attitude of male & female B.Ed. Teachers towards In-service teacher training programmes.*

Table – 4 : Significance difference of attitude male and female teachers.

Male Teachers (N ₁ =27)		Female Teachers (N ₂ = 38)		CR=Value
M ₁ = 15.96	$t_1 = 1.55$	M ₂ = 15.81	$t_2 = 1.38$	CR = 0.405

Interpretation : Table No. 4 - indicates that our calculated values of CR -score is 0.405 which is less than the critical value at the degree of freedom 63 of both the levels of significance 0.001 and 0.05 level. So there was no significance difference between the attitude of Male and Female towards In-service training program. So null hypothesis has been accepted. Thus we can say that male and female B.Ed. teachers have the same attitude towards I.S.T.T.P.

Hypothesis – 5 *There is no significant difference between attitude of Govt. Aided and Self finance male teachers towards In-service teacher training programmes.*

Table – 5 Comparison of Attitude between Govt. & Self Finance college Male Teaches.

Govt. Aided College		Self finance College		Cr-Value
Male Teacher of Govt. Aided Colleges (N ₁ =31)		Male Self Finance College Colleges (N ₁ =34)		
Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	t=0 .902
M1=16.25	$t_1 = 1.35$	M1=15.73	$t_1 = 1.65$	

INTERPRETATION: Table No. 5 reveals that the obtain 't' value is 0.902 with df. 25 which is not significant even at 0.01 level of confidence with of 25. It seems to be safe to interoperate that there is no significant difference between the attitude of male teachers of Govt. Aided Colleges and male teachers of Self finance colleges towards in-service teacher training programmes. A little difference that exists maybe due to sampling error.

Thus the null hypothesis that “There is no significant difference between attitude of Govt. Aided and Self finance B.Ed. College male Teacher towards In-service teacher training program.” Is accepted.

Hypothesis – 6 : *There is no significant difference between attitude of Govt. Aided and Self finance B.Ed. college female teachers towards In-service teacher education programmes.*

Table-6 Comparison of Attitude between Govt. & Self Finance college Female Teaches

Govt. Aided College		Self finance College		Cr-Value
Female Teacher of Govt. Aided Colleges		Female Teacher Self Finance Colleges		
Mean	S.D.	Mean	S.D.	
M ₁ =15.84	s ₁ =1.34	M ₁ =15.78	s ₁ =1.43	

INTERPRETATION: Table No. 6- indicates that our calculated value of CR score is 0.136 which was less than the critical values at the degree of freedom 36 of both the levels of significance 0.01 and 0.05 levels with df. 36. So hypothesis has been accepted. Thus we can say that female teachers of Govt. Aided and Self finance B.Ed. Colleges have same attitude toward In-Service teacher training programmes.

FINDINGS: (1)-The B.Ed. Teacher of Govt. Aided Colleges have high favorable attitude towards In-service teacher training programmes.(2)The B.Ed. Teacher of Self Finance Colleges have high favorable attitude towards In-service teacher training programmes.(3)Type of the Institution (Govt. Aided & Self Finance) does not exert significant influence on the attitude of B.Ed. teachers towards In-service teacher training programmes. (4) The sex does not exert significant influence on the attitude of B.Ed. Teachers towards In-service teacher training programmes.

Educational Implications:- Educational research must begin with a felt problem and must return to that problem with a proposed solution or fresh knowledge leading to the solution of that

problem. “In service teacher training programme” is definitely a welcome means in the teaching community to equip everyone in the community to face the new challenges and to play important and significant role in their competency. The topic of the study is of enormous importance in the field of education these have been stated under following heads:

- The findings of the study may be discussed with the trainee and trainer of the In-service teacher training programmes and efforts can be made to develop insight in them.
- To develop awareness among supervisors and administrators ,so that they may provide proper and essential facilities to the teachers who have completed In-service training programmes such as incentives and other facilities to promote interest in the teachers towards I.S.T.T.P.
- The finding of the study may suggest the policy makers to make such policies which may reduce the gap between Govt. Aided and Self-finance teacher regarding the I.ST.T.P.
- The institutional heads should encourage the teachers of their institutes to attend the in-service teacher training programmes most frequently and enthusiastically.

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